

COOKSTOVE USABILITY CRITERIA TABLE

Fuel Convenience	Cooking Performance	Operability	Maintenance	Comfort	Location-Specific Needs
Fuel availability	Firepower Range	Tending/refueling frequency	Routine maintenance	Cooking area soot deposits	Space heating
Fuel preparation	Firepower control	Tending/refueling effort	Long-term maintenance	Perceived smoke exposure	Insect repellent
	Cooking speed	Fuel feed entry size		Perceived safety	Lighting
	Versatility	Visibility of fire		Pot soot deposits	Portability
		Ease of lighting		Cooking height	Water heating
		Fire start-up delay		Stove aesthetics	Food drying/smoking
		User error		Perceived durability	<i>(Additional needs may be added by test administrator)</i>
		User instruction		Perceived value	
				Taste	